

Some Similarities Between Classical Statistical and Quantum Mechanics?

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Quantum mechanics is often compared with classical mechanics because both may deal with a single particle subject to a potential. Classical mechanics is said to be deterministic describing $x(t)$ and its derivatives i.e showing how a particle moves and accelerates while bound state quantum mechanics produces a real wavefunction $W(x)$ such that $W(x)W(x)$ yields a spatial density profile. The comparison is carried further with the correspondence principle which states that at high energy levels quantum mechanics should mimic classical mechanics.

Classical mechanics does not simply describe $x(t)$ and its derivatives i.e. deterministic motion. It also includes two body scattering, force and torque balances for a stationary object etc. In the case of the classical statistical mechanics of an equilibrium ideal gas, the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution in the absence of a potential is $C_1 \exp(-pp/(2mT))$. If a potential $V(x)$ is added, one may find $P(x)$ two different ways using Newtonian ideas. The first is to consider the gas as a collective entity like a tiny macroscopic classical object at x . Then one may argue that equilibrium means the system is stationary and apply Newtonian statics i.e. a balance of pressures and $-dV/dx$ to obtain $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ as is often done in textbooks.

Alternatively, one may consider a single particle and apply Newtonian mechanics differently, namely use a conservation of energy equation: $p_1^2/2m + V(x_1) = p_2^2/2m + V(x_2)$. Again one obtains $\exp(-V(x)/T)$.

The spatial part of probability may be based on Newtonian mechanics indicating that it is not stochastic. The stochastic function is $C_1 \exp(-pp/2mT)$. Interestingly, however, the two Newtonian approaches are different with respect to a single particle. A collective nonmoving set of particles acts as a stationary object, yet within it each particle seems to be "bouncing" off of an imaginary wall creating pressure. Thus one has an impulse free particle picture yet obtains the correct result $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. Alternatively one may think of a single particle accelerating which it does if it is not colliding with other particles. This is a very different picture of the single particle than of one bouncing back and forth hitting an imaginary wall. In fact, there is usually a wall holding the gas together and pressure and bouncing particles are the real picture there, but within the gas one would normally think of a single particle accelerating. Nevertheless there are two scenarios which yield the same result. The idea of pressure balance is more in keeping with an overall statistical picture of the gas. In other words, one may actually ignore the idea of following a single particle as it accelerates. (That is not to say that single particle acceleration does not exist - it does.)

Quantum mechanics we argue is a statistical theory. In the case of a single bound particle one has a momentum distribution $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. One may apply conservation of average energy at each x to obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation. In such a picture, like with the statistical mechanical gas, we argue that one may imagine impulse hits with the potential instead of considering acceleration. The quantity $v_{rms}(x)$ from $K_{Eclassical} = .5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ does display acceleration, but this is a mathematical average. As energy levels become higher the correspondence principle is said to apply, but a classical particle exhibits acceleration. The quantum bound state does not, but like in the case of the statistical mechanical gas it may be that two scenarios lead to the

same result. In other words, the quantum bound $W(x)$ still has crests and troughs, but with low resolution one may only see an envelope roughly touching $W(x)$ which matches a classical $C2/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity. Given that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory it may not be necessary to have it explicitly display acceleration.

Ideal Gas and Two Ways to Obtain $\exp(-V(x)/T)$

A Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for no potential $V(x)$ is: $C1 \exp(-pp/2mT)$ ((1)). This is a stochastic result which may be obtained in a number of ways e.g. maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to an average energy constraint or using reaction balance for two body elastic collisions. The question is what happens if one adds a potential? One may use Newtonian mechanics in two different ways to obtain the result.

First one imagines a small box of gas at x as a macroscopic entity subject to Newton's laws of static i.e. the force at one end of the box (at x) must equal the force at the other end $x+dx$ plus $-dV/dx$ density(x). Using the ideal gas law which is consistent with ((1)) one may find $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. The point we wish to make is that if one is considering pressure at x then each particle is like a free one bouncing back and forth against imaginary walls. There is no notion of acceleration even though a single particle actually does accelerate as it moves from x to $x+dx$. This is an impulse picture of the system and at the walls of the box it is this scenario which exists. Within the gas, however, one places an "imaginary" wall and considers pressure striking it.

Another Newtonian approach is to consider a single particle in the gas which does accelerate as it moves from one point to another without colliding with other particles. If there are say 10 particles with momentum $p1$ at $x1$ then these are linked to a momentum probability $f(p1,x)$. One has $p1^2/2m + V(x1) = p2^2/2m + V(x2)$ so at $x2$ there should now be 10 particles with $p1$. This suggests an overall probability based on a function of the constant E i.e. $g(E)$. Given that the MB distribution is $\exp(-pp/2mT)$ then $g(E) = E$ and one has $C1 \exp(- pp/2mT - V(x)/T)$.

Thus one may obtain the spatial $P(x) = \exp(-V(x)/T)$ using Newtonian mechanics in very different ways. The point we wish to stress is that single particles behave in a different manner in each scenario. In the first which is based on pressure, single particles bounce back and forth without acceleration in a tiny box. They are like free particles at x . The alternative scenario considers a single particle which accelerates according to Newton's law as long as it is not colliding. Thus two different scenarios lead to the same result and each may have its advantages.

Application to Quantum Mechanics

We suggest that this idea may be applied to quantum mechanics. The idea of the particle bouncing back and forth and creating part of the overall pressure while acting like a free particle at x is more closely linked to statistical notions than that of a single particle accelerating. We argue that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory based on free particles represented by a "strange" probability $\exp(ipx)$ which incorporates dynamics. A distribution is created by:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

Quantum mechanics is also described by a distribution of free particles at x . The difference is two fold. First there is interference i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ contains $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which may be positive and negative. The second is that spatial density is given by $W^*(x)W(x)$. Nevertheless one may create an average energy conservation equation at each x i.e.

$$\sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

Here we are using a conditional probability: $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$.

Like in the statistical mechanical case for pressure balance there is no notion of acceleration of a single particle (in the quantum case $\exp(ipx)$). On average $v_{rms}(x)$ from $KE(x) = .5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ accelerates, but it is a mathematical average. Like with the classical statistical mechanical scenario of a little box with bouncing free particles, one may obtain correct results. This is an impulse scenario and one may write $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. As n in E_n becomes very large, the correspondence principle suggests that one should see classical mechanical behaviour. One, however, still has a statistical theory. Crests in $W^*(x)W(x)$ may become narrow so that with poor resolution one may only see an envelope touching the crests. In such a case $C^2/v(x)$ a classical density matches the envelope, but the quantum mechanical picture is still statistical and does not represent acceleration. Only if one associates $v_{rms}(x)$ with the high n quantum result does one obtain deterministic classical mechanics. We argue that like in the statistical mechanical case, this may not be a problem. There, two very different Newtonian scenarios were used for a single particle and yet both yield a correct result. For the quantum case, the statistical free particle impulse scenario appears to describe lower n results well and may even be applicable for high n in the sense that motion may not really be a smooth translation as in classical mechanics. Nevertheless as the correspondence principle indicates there may be some links with a deterministic picture i.e. $C^2/v(x)$ just as considering acceleration of a single particle in classical statistical mechanics gives a correct result, but perhaps applies to a low resolution description i.e. classical mechanical distances are usually large compared to quantum ones.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that given the MB distribution for an ideal gas with no potential $V(x)$, one may use Newtonian mechanics in two different ways to find the dependence on an introduced $V(x)$. First one may consider a tiny box of gas as a macroscopic object at x and apply Newtonian statics at x and $x+dx$. Then each single particle in the tiny box bounces back and forth like a free particle and creates a pressure. Balancing pressure (ideal gas law) at x and $x+dx$ such that the difference is density $(-dV/dx)$ one finds $\text{density}(x) = C \exp(-V(x)/T)$.

Alternatively one may consider that a single particle which does not collide, accelerates according to Newton's second law. This implies that there is an overall probability constancy based on E because $p^2/2m$ is part of the MB no potential result. Thus two very different Newtonian single particle descriptions i.e. a bouncing free particle and an accelerating particle lead to the same $P(x)$. The bouncing particles in the tiny box scenario is more of a statistical

picture whereas the accelerating single particle is deterministic. Thus one might solve the overall MB problem without any notion of an accelerating particle.

We argue that this approach may be analogous to a quantum bound particle. Quantum mechanics considers a distribution of free particles each described by $\exp(ipx)$. Thus: $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of momentum distribution. Unlike the classical statistical gas, quantum mechanics has interference. Like the classical gas, however, there is a momentum distribution of free particles at each x point. In other words there is no notion of $\exp(ipx)$ accelerating. Establishing an average conservation of energy equation leads to the time-independent Schrodinger equation. The question becomes: What happens for high E_n i.e. high energy levels? According to the correspondence principle one should see classical mechanical behaviour, but quantum mechanics is a statistical theory. Thus for high n , crests are very narrow and with poor resolution one would only see an envelope passing roughly through the peaks of $W^*(x)W(x)$. This envelope is equivalent to $C^2/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity. Normally, however, a classical bound particle is described by its acceleration, not by an unusual density proportional to the amount of time the particle spends within dx . Quantum mechanics, however, is a statistical theory. As a result, it may only partially describe the classical situation e.g. through $C^2/v(x)$ i.e. the classical theory may be a low resolution one. Furthermore the narrow peaks may be linked to high resolution quantum effects even at high energy.